

Characterization and tests of the HTS tape and the preliminary pancake for the RSFCL of the SCARLET project

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Abstract — Resistive Superconducting Fault Current Limiters (RSFCL) are a promising solution for the protection of medium and high voltage DC and AC power links. They are particularly needed if superconducting power cables are integrated into the DC grid to ease design requirements of the electrical system. In the framework of the European project SCARLET, this solution is studied for the protection strategy of a 1GW offshore wind power export system employing MVDC superconducting cable operating at 50 kV DC. This is achieved by selecting an HTS tape with suitable properties and designing the RSFCL with a proper number of parallel tapes wound in bifilar pancake coils. This work reports on the test characterization campaign carried out for an HTS tape candidate for the RSFCL for the SCARLET project. DC and AC tests are performed at both low current and overcurrent regimes, and the temperature-dependent resistance of the tape was also determined. A demonstrator pancake with 6 stainless-steel tapes and 4 HTS tapes was manufactured, intentionally limiting the HTS content as this preliminary stage of the project focused primarily on validating the feasibility of the manufacturing process. The results of the experimental campaign on this pancake are also presented, highlighting key design considerations for the subsequent fabrication of the final device.

Index Terms — RSFCL, HTS tape, Tape characterization, overcurrent tests.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of advanced protection strategies is a key enabler for the reliable operation of emerging MVDC transmission systems and multi-terminal DC (MTDC) grids. Among the different technological solutions, Resistive Superconducting Fault Current Limiters (RSFCLs) have attracted considerable attention because of their ability to remain invisible to the system during normal operation while providing a fast and effective limitation of fault currents [1][2][3]. This functionality is especially valuable when superconducting cables are introduced in MVDC point-to-point connections or MTDC configurations, where fault management otherwise poses critical challenges. Within the scope of the European SCARLET project [4], RSFCLs are investigated as a protection component for a 1 GW offshore wind export link employing a 50 kV superconducting MVDC cable. In this scheme, the

RSFCL, associated in series with the HTS cable, is designed for ± 50 kV/10 kA [5].

This work presents the tests results of a preliminary pancake of the RSFCL for the SCARLET project. The RSFCL concept relies on the transition of High Temperature Superconducting (HTS) tapes from the superconducting to the resistive state during faults. This transition not only restricts the amplitude of short-circuit currents but also requires the superconducting material to absorb and dissipate significant energy in a controlled manner. To meet these requirements, the choice of the HTS tape and the definition of the coil architecture are central design aspects [6]. The approach explored here is based on winding parallel HTS tapes into bifilar pancake coils, which can subsequently be combined in series or in parallel to fulfill the voltage and current specified by the project. It is worth noting how previous implementations of bifilar pancake coils for RSFCL [7][8][9][10][11] typically operate at currents substantially lower than the 10 kA required in the SCARLET project. This underscores the demanding current rating targeted in the design of the device, which will be assessed during the next stages of the project under subcooled LN₂ operating conditions. In this framework, each pancake represents the basic building block of the full device. A single unit is designed to sustain a rated voltage of ~ 2 kV, while the connection of multiple pancakes will provide the voltage capability required by the final device.

Following this context, the results of a dedicated experimental campaign on a candidate HTS tape are first presented, including DC and AC tests under nominal and overcurrent conditions, as well as temperature-dependent resistance characterization. Then, as an intermediate step toward the final device, a demonstrator pancake coil is manufactured and tested in LN₂, allowing validation of fabrication methods and assessment of performance. This preliminary pancake replicates the design of the final coils, despite six of its ten parallel conductors being replaced by stainless steel tapes to reduce the consumption of HTS tape.

By addressing performance at both tape and coil level, the present results not only meet a key milestone of the SCARLET project but also offer fundamental insights for scaling the design to a full-scale RSFCL prototype.

II. TESTS ON THE HTS TAPE SELECTED FOR THE RSFCL

A. HTS tape selection

The selection process of the commercially available HTS tape for the RSFCL project accounted for multiple factors related to

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Fig. 1. (a) Selected tape cross-section (not in scale) as declared by the manufacturer. (b) Set-up used to test straight segments of the HTS tape at 77 K.

the device's operating requirements. First, a high critical current (I_c) is advantageous, as it reduces the number of parallel connections and the number of parallel pancake coils required; I_c homogeneity along the tape length has to be ensured by the manufacturer, as local fluctuations could compromise the predictability of the current-limiting behavior. In addition, the availability of a strong thermal buffer is essential, as it allows for a shorter effective tape length while ensuring sufficient heat absorption during fault events, and offering sufficient mechanical robustness for the winding process. Finally, the conductor has to be available in sufficiently long lengths to allow the construction of multiple coils without splicing.

Taking all these factors into consideration, a 12 mm wide tape supplied by Shanghai Superconductor Technology (SST) was selected. The manufacturer was able to guarantee an improved I_c compared to its standard supplies (≥ 650 A at 77 K) and stainless-steel lamination equal to 80 μm per side. This corresponds to the maximum available lamination thickness manufacturable by the supplier in continuous lengths; this enhances the thermal buffer during fault events and reduces the required limitation length. Fig. 1a shows a scheme of the tape cross-section. For the project purposes, approximately 1000 meters of this conductor were procured.

B. HTS tape characterization

The selected HTS tape was characterized to verify its compliance with the defined project criteria, carrying out a series of electrical and thermal tests.

The critical current, measured in liquid nitrogen at 77 K, 72 K, and 68 K, consistently exceeded the manufacturer's specifications, showing good homogeneity across the five segments tested. Fig. 1b shows the set-up for the 77 K tests, carried out on a 60 cm long sample. At 77 K, the I_c was above 770 A while the n -value was around 24.3. Compared to this value, the I_c was around 40% higher at 72 K, and around 72% higher at 68 K.

Fig. 2. $R(T)$ obtained in two labs, below and above T_{amb} , for different tape samples of the same SST batch.

Another relevant parameter for RSFCL sizing concerns the evaluation of the tape resistance after the transition to the normal state. $R(T)$ was tested from 50 K to room temperature using a cryocooler at the RSE laboratory, and from room temperature up to 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at SuperGrid Institute laboratory, on tape samples belonging to the same batch. The resulting profiles were consistent across laboratories and temperature ranges, with resistivity values falling within the manufacturer's specifications (Fig. 2). For completeness, additional samples from different batches of the same supply were tested at the RSE lab, exhibiting differences in the $R(T)$ profiles. This observation indicates the need for further investigation into the actual uniformity of the tape architecture across the entire production.

Then, AC overcurrent tests were performed at 50 Hz and at 77 K and 68 K, increasing the current amplitude in subsequent tests. It should be noted that overcurrent tests were performed under AC conditions due to technical limitations of the available setup, where only an AC power source could deliver the required energy to the tape. This does not affect the validity of the results, as the total energy input, critical for thermal and electrical assessment, can be achieved and assessed under either AC or DC excitation.

Fig. 3a and Fig. 3c show the current and electric field profile acquired during the tests at 77 K and 68 K respectively, where the expected current limitation behaviour can be observed after the first period. For the 77 K tests, the current was increased until the peak electric field reached approximately 100 V/m, while for the 68 K, a peak value around 120 V/m was reached. Both these peaks occurred during the second cycle. The critical current was verified after each applied current level, confirming the absence of degradation.

From the measured voltage and current signals ($v_{\text{exp}}(t)$ and $I_{\text{exp}}(t)$), the instantaneous power per unit length $P_{\text{exp}}(t)$ was computed as in Eq. (1) for all the AC tests, considering also the limited inductance of the short tape sample.

$$P_{\text{exp}}(t) = I_{\text{exp}}(t) \left(v_{\text{exp}}(t) - L \frac{dI_{\text{exp}}(t)}{dt} \right) \quad (1)$$

The instantaneous temperature $T_{\text{tape}}(t)$ along the whole tape was then obtained by solving the adiabatic energy-balance

Fig. 3. Applied overcurrent (top) and corresponding acquired electric fields (bottom) for the selected tape at (a) 77 K and (c) 68 K. Derived trends for the instantaneous temperature (top) and power dissipated by the tape (bottom) at (b) 77 K and (d) 68 K; in the legends, the curves colors correspond to the same overcurrent tests of the sub-figures (a) and (c). The captions report the peak values of the quantities reached after three current cycles.

equation Eq. (2), where the thermal capacity per unit length $c_{tape}(T_{tape})$ is estimated from the multilayer structure of the tape of Fig. 1(a) and the known temperature-dependent properties of the single materials [12].

$$c_{tape}(T_{tape}) \frac{dT_{tape}(t)}{dt} = P_{exp}(t) \quad (2)$$

For the 77 K case (Fig. 3b), when the amplitude of the applied current was 1550.9 A, the peak power dissipated (occurring when the electric field peaks) was equal to 118 kW/m while the tape temperature reached 310.5 K at the end of that test. For the 68 K case (Fig. 3d), when the amplitude of the applied current was 2530.1 A, the peak power dissipated was equal to 260 kW/m while the tape temperature reached 358 K at the end of that test.

Finally, sustained DC current tests at 77 K were carried out, applying a current approximately 110% of I_c for 5 minutes and a current around 100% of I_c for 2 hours. During these tests, the temporal evolution of the electric field remained stable above the 1 μ V/cm threshold, indicating that neither the sample resistance nor its temperature exhibited any appreciable variation. A subsequent critical current measurement confirmed the absence of degradation.

III. TEST ON THE PRELIMINARY RSFCL PANCAKE

A. Design criteria for the SCARLET RSFCL demonstrator

Based on the characteristics of the selected tape, the RSFCL main parameters have been defined in SCARLET Deliverable D5.2 [13] for various cases of DC system voltage and power flow configurations during nominal and faulty conditions. As an example, for a 1 GW ± 50 kV_{DC} offshore wind export system, a minimum critical current of 11000 A_{DC}, and a worst-case energy absorption capability of 21 MJ during 70 ms are required. To illustrate the impact and the expected behaviour of the RSFCL when interacting with the DC system, a worst-case scenario has been simulated. A pole-to-pole fault is assumed to occur at only 500 m from the cable end, on the converter side. Four parallel converters feed the fault, and the DC circuit breakers located at each converter bus are designed to clear the fault in less than 5 ms, except for one breaker that fails to operate for unspecified reasons. As a backup protection measure, the AC circuit breaker on the 420 kV_{rms} AC grid side of the same converter operates, clearing the fault within a maximum of 70 ms. Using the commercially available tape characterized in this work, an RSFCL with a total limitation length of approximately 8330 m is included in this grid. With the RSFCL, the peak short-circuit current is reduced by almost a factor of two, and the fault duration is significantly shortened, as in Fig. 4. This combined effect mitigates thermal and electrodynamic stress on the superconducting cable and reduces the risk that the healthy sections of the cable overheat and undergo potential damage. It is worth noting that the estimated total limitation length would not be technically feasible for a single winding; therefore, the demonstrator developed in this project has been conceived as a modular unit which, when replicated, provides an overall limitation length consistent with the simulated requirements.

Fig. 4. Worst case short-circuit currents with and without the final SCARLET RSFCL demonstrator, for the fault case considered in the simulated grid. The fault occurs at 2 s.

TABLE I
DESIGN PARAMETERS FOR BOTH THE RSFCL FOR THE SCARLET PROJECT
AND THE PRELIMINARY PANCAKE

	<i>RSFCL of the SCARLET project</i>	<i>Preliminary pancake</i>
<i>N° of pancakes in series</i>	4	1
<i>N° of anti-inductive HTS tapes in each pancake</i>	10 (divided into 5 paths: 2 parallel tapes per path)	4 (divided into 2 paths; the other 3 are realized with 2 SS tapes each)
<i>Pancakes inner radius [mm]</i>		250.0
<i>Pancakes outer radius [mm]</i>		850.0
<i>Insulation between HTS paths [mm]</i>		~ 2.0
<i>Limitation length (each tape in each pancake) [m]</i>	~ 26.0	~ 22.5
<i>Total HTS tape length [m/pancake]</i>	~ 260.0	~ 90.0 (the remaining is SS tape)

The design of the single unit of the modular RSFCL is based on winding conductive parallel paths in form of pancakes, in a bifilar and anti-inductive configuration [14][16]. The total limiting length of the pancake corresponds to the sum of the lengths of the individual paths. In defining the coil architecture, additional practical constraints specific to the SCARLET demonstrator were also considered. For example, the outer diameter of each pancake must comply with the cryostat dimensions used for subsequent subcooled-LN₂ testing, while the number of series pancakes is limited by the cryostat height. The number of anti-inductive parallel HTS paths had to remain compatible with the available winding space, while still meeting the 10 kA target of the final device based on the measured critical current at 77 K and its extrapolation to lower temperatures.

Table I summarizes the main characteristics of the SCARLET RSFCL, composed of four pancakes in series. Each pancake contains five conductive paths, each formed by two parallel HTS tapes. It should be noted that, within the framework of the project, the final device will also serve as a representative RSFCL, designed to address the main technical challenges of the full-scale system, although it will not be rated for the full ± 50 kV.

Fig. 5. Top view of the preliminary pancake made for the RSFCL of the SCARLET project.

B. Preliminary pancake realization

A milestone in the SCARLET project required verifying the feasibility of winding the pancake using the same design, features, and fabrication techniques foreseen for the final device. To this end, a preliminary pancake was fabricated, whose main characteristics are compared to those of the SCARLET RSFCL in Table I. During the manufacturing process, care was taken to respect the minimum bending diameter and maximum mechanical stress specified by the HTS supplier to avoid any degradation of the HTS tape. Only two out of the five parallel paths of the preliminary pancake were realized with HTS tapes, while the remaining paths were wound with 12-mm-wide stainless-steel tapes with comparable mechanical properties. This approach was adopted to assess the feasibility of the device's mechanical construction while minimizing HTS consumption, as only about 100 m of spare tape were available for this intermediate stage of the project. Then, during the power tests, only the HTS paths were supplied.

The tapes were electrically insulated from each other by means of a corrugated fiber glass spacer assuring a gap of approximately 2 mm between HTS tapes. The same insulation type demonstrated efficiency under cryogenic conditions in an RSFCL developed within the FASTGRID project [15]. A photo of the fabricated preliminary pancake is shown in Fig. 5.

Although the preliminary pancake presented here is not intended to carry the full current at the target temperature, it is a structural proof-of-concept of the final RSFCL coil. Its geometry, winding layout, and manufacturing process have been reproduced exactly, ensuring that this prototype effectively validates the feasibility of the full-scale design.

C. Preliminary pancake testing

The critical currents of the two HTS paths were first measured by inserting the pancake into a properly sized box and immersing it in liquid nitrogen at 77 K. Voltage taps were soldered directly onto the HTS tapes, close to the terminations, a solution

Fig. 6. (a) I_c power-law from DC tests (measured and extrapolated). (b) AC losses from AC tests with an inset of the instantaneous dissipated power of HTS path n°1 during the test with $I_{max} = 1291$ A. (b) Self- and mutual-inductances from AC tests (extrapolated). Results refer to the two HTS paths of the preliminary pancake.

implemented in the preliminary pancake, but potentially not adopted in the final device, as it was considered risky for the tape integrity. During testing, the HTS paths were supplied separately, maintaining a safety margin on the electric field with respect to the $1 \mu\text{V}/\text{cm}$ criterion, and the I_c was extrapolated using a power-law fit (Fig. 6a). Both HTS paths exhibited an I_c approximately 11% lower than the sum of two isolated straight single tapes. This reduction may be attributed to tape handling during winding, local magnetic fields that persisted despite the anti-inductive design, or a slightly uneven current distribution between the parallel conductors; however, at this stage, current sharing between tapes could not be directly assessed.

Sustained DC current tests were performed on the individual HTS paths with an applied current above 90% of I_c for one minute showed no detectable heating. These results confirm stable

DC performance under near-critical conditions. However, further investigations are required to assess the current sharing and overall behavior when supplying the complete pancake, rather than individual paths.

Finally, AC tests at 50 Hz were also performed supplying individually the two HTS paths, despite the RSFCL will be used in nominal DC conditions. These AC tests were carried out to enable straightforward calculation of self- and mutual inductances and to compare the AC losses with tape-level measurements. Such measurements provide key indications of winding quality and anti-inductive design effectiveness, which are objectives of the preliminary pancake within the current stage of the SCARLET project, aimed at validating the manufacturability and correctness of the coil assembly.

The trends of the AC loss per unit of length followed an expected trend as a function of the ratio between the amplitude of the AC current and the paths I_c s (Fig. 6b), indicating that HTS path n°2 exhibited slightly higher losses, which may be related to its lower critical current. The AC losses of the straight sample are also shown in the same plot: these losses are considerably lower than those of the preliminary pancake paths, probably due to the residual magnetic field acting on the winding. Fig. 6b also shows an inset of the instantaneous losses for HTS path n°1 of the preliminary pancake when the AC peak current is 1291 A. It can be observed that the average power over one cycle is not zero, which indicates the presence of AC losses. Then, looking at the phase shift between the acquired voltage and current signals, the self-inductance per unit length of both HTS paths was detected and confirmed to be nearly identical (left axis in Fig. 6c), as expected from the symmetric design. During the test on one HTS path, the voltage signal acquired from the second HTS path, not supplied with current, allows for an estimation of the mutual inductance between the two paths (right axis in Fig. 6c). This is approximately one order of magnitude lower than the self-inductances, due to the anti-inductive design of the winding. The increasing trend of self- and mutual inductances with the current amplitude was also expected from the literature [17][18].

Overall, the results confirm the feasibility of the winding approach and demonstrate that the electrical performance of the prototype pancake meets the expectations for the final device. Owing to these results, four full-scale HTS demonstration pancakes have already been manufactured. Upcoming tests include individual pancake characterization, verification of DC nominal-current capability, and assessment of current sharing among the five parallel paths. Then, the pancakes will be assembled in a cryostat and operated in subcooled conditions to confirm 10 kA_{DC} performance without degradation. Finally, limitation tests will be carried out on the complete RSFCL demonstrator under subcooled, high-voltage DC short-circuit conditions.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work has reported on the experimental characterization of a 12-mm HTS tape from Shanghai Superconductor Technology, selected as a candidate conductor for the RSFCL of the

SCARLET project. The tape, reinforced with 80- μm stainless-steel lamination on both sides, exhibited suitable performance for the project needs: a sufficiently homogenous critical current exceeding 650 A at 77 K, overcurrent tolerance and a proper temperature-dependent resistance. These results confirm that the conductor meets the operational requirements of the device.

To fulfill the project milestones, a preliminary pancake coil, whose design is identical to the final superconducting pancake coils of the RSFCL prototype, was successfully fabricated by combining two HTS paths with stainless-steel dummy windings. Tests under both DC and AC currents in liquid nitrogen verified the proper operation of the HTS turns, thus validating the feasibility of the proposed coil concept and the associated manufacturing process. Compared with earlier bifilar pancake implementations, the SCARLET design targets much higher operating currents, making the preliminary pancake a key validation step toward a 10 kA-rated RSFCL coil.

Future work expected from the SCARLET project will address scaling to the full RSFCL configuration, including optimization of current distribution among parallel paths and assessment of long-term stability under fault conditions.

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